

Solar Electron Accelerator Cell and Electron Batteries (SEACEB)

Mostly Solar cells don't work in cloudy weather. But the amount of Electromagnetic energy content is high enough in the atmosphere. Solar Electron Accelerator Cell works in such an engineered way that even with dim light the solar cell can produce high amount energy.

The electron battery on the other hand is a battery based on trapping electrons and creating a potential difference because of which the battery acts as a electromechanical battery and can last for 100s of years.

The details of the invention are classified and will never be shared at all. The Solar Electron Accelerator Cell and Electron Batteries is a part of Systematic Invention Unit.

The screenshot shows the Paperpal Plagiarism Check interface. At the top left, it says "Paperpal Plagiarism Check" with a "Standard" filter. On the top right, it says "In partnership with Turnitin". Below this, the "Overview" section is active. A large yellow box on the left states "No Similarity Detected". To the right, a message reads: "We detected no similarity in your document. Check another document for similarity." Below this, the "Uploaded Documents" section lists "SEACEB.docx" with a Microsoft Word icon. A preview of the document content is shown below the filename, with some text blurred. At the bottom right of the document preview, there is a blue padlock icon, indicating that the document is locked.